

Vanadium: Part XVI. Oxo-Vanadium (IV) Schiff Base Complexes

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The paper describes the syntheses and characterisation of a group of oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes of (a) bidentate, monobasic Schiff bases and of (b) quadridentate, dibasic Schiff bases. The complexes are 5 co-ordinate, paramagnetic (1.54–1.85 B.M.) and show vanadyl stretching frequency at $989 \pm 39 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and coordinated C = N stretching at $1617 \pm 17 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Bidentate Schiff bases derived from arylamines provide a weaker ligand field than those of the alkylamines. Square pyramidal structure is indicated in solid state and in chloroform. In pyridine all bands move to higher energy. The *d*-orbital ordering $d_{xy} < d_{xz}, d_{yz} < d_{x^2-y^2} < d_{z^2}$ has been preferred to an alternative $d_{xy} < d_{x^2-y^2} < d_{xz}, d_{yz} < d_{z^2}$. The complexes of the quadridentate Schiff bases give comparable spectra in solid state, in chloroform and in pyridine. This failure to add a sixth ligand has been interpreted as the result of saturation in the acceptor ability of oxo-vanadium (IV) due to strong σ -donation by the equatorial ligands.

The oxo-vanadium (IV) ion with a d^1 electronic configuration is being actively investigated at present times¹. The earlier papers^{2,3} from this laboratory were directed mainly towards the syntheses and characterisation of a series of oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes of a variety of coordinating ligands. The complexing ability of the Schiff bases with various transition metal ions including oxo-vanadium (IV) is reflected in the appearance of several papers and review articles^{4–12}. This paper describes the results of our investigations on the syntheses and electronic spectral properties of several complexes of this transition metal ion with bidentate and quadridentate Schiff bases obtained from substituted salicylaldehydes and aryl monoamines or alkyl/aryldiamines.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the compounds : Compounds of bidentate Schiff bases: Ethanol solution of X-salicylaldehyde (·02 mole) was refluxed with an arylamine (·02 mole) in ethanol for 15–20 minutes on a steam bath. Ethanol solution of syrupy vanadyl chloride (·01 mole) was treated with (·02 mole) sodium acetate and filtered. The filtrate was added to the

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2. R. L. Dutta and S. Lahiry, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **38**, 1001; 1962, **39**, 860, 871; 1963, **40**, 53, 67, 857, 863; 1964, **41**, 62.
3. R. L. Dutta and S. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 273, 290, 296, 306, 381.
4. S. Yamada, *Coord. Chem. Revs.*, 1966, **1**, 415.
5. L. Sacconi and U. Campigli, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 606.
6. L. J. Boucher, E. C. Tynan and T. F. Yen, *ibid.*, 1968, **7**, 371.
7. L. J. Boucher and T. F. Yen, *ibid.*, 1968, **7**, 2665.
8. L. J. Boucher and T. F. Yen, *ibid.*, 1969, **8**, 689.
9. S. Yamada and Y. Kuge, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1969, **42**, 152.
10. R. L. Dutta and G. P. Sen Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 738.
11. P. Pfeiffer, T. Hesse, H. Pfitzner, W. Schell and H. Thielert, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1937, **149**, 217.
12. P. Pfeiffer, H. Thielert and H. Glaser, *ibid.*, 1939, **152**, 145.

ethanolic Schiff base solution and refluxed for 30–60 minutes. The product, often greenish yellow, separated out from the solution. It was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in a desiccator. The compounds of this type are quite stable and may be recrystallised from chloroform, where possible, without any precaution against oxidation. The compounds are usually soluble in chloroform and pyridine but less so in methanol, ethanol, benzene and ether.

Compounds of quadridentate Schiff bases : The Schiff bases were prepared by the interaction of the substituted salicylaldehydes and the respective diamines. Ethanol solution of the Schiff base was then allowed to react with vanadyl acetate as described above. The Schiff base [(5,6 benzo-sal)₂—tm] was dissolved in dimethylformamide instead of ethanol. All these complexes are distinctly less soluble than the complexes of the bidentate ligands.

The characterisation data of the compounds are presented in Table I.

TABLE I

*Summary of Physical and Analytical Data for Oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes**

Compound	M.P. or Decomp. Point	Analysis			
		%V		%N	
		Found	Calcd	Found	Calcd.
[VO(H-Sal-NC ₆ H ₅) ₂]	233–235°C	11.08	11.11	6.01	6.10
[VO(H-Sal-NC ₆ H ₄ -pCl) ₂]	252–254	9.48	9.65	5.40	5.30
[VO(H-Sal-NC ₆ H ₄ -pOCH ₃) ₂]	221–223	9.74	9.82	5.50	5.39
[VO(H-Sal-NC ₆ H ₄ -pSO ₂ NH ₂) ₂]	> 300	8.10	8.26	8.88	9.07
[VO(5, Cl-Sal-NC ₆ H ₅) ₂]	264–266	9.63	9.65	5.40	5.30
[VO(5,6 Benzo-Sal-NC ₆ H ₅) ₂]	298–300	9.18	9.12	5.08	5.01
[VO(5,6 Benzo-Sal-NC ₆ H ₄ -pCl) ₂]	293–295	8.06	8.12	4.70	4.45
[VO(5,6 Benzo-Sal-NC ₆ H ₄ -pOCH ₃) ₂]	275–277	8.06	8.23	4.80	4.52
[VO(4,OH-Sal-NC ₆ H ₄ -pCl) ₂]	> 300	9.18	9.10	4.70	5.00
[VO(4,OH-Sal-NC ₆ H ₄ -pOCH ₃) ₂]	> 300	9.07	9.25	5.10	5.08
[VO(H-Sal) ₂ -en]	288–290	14.98	15.30	8.32	8.40
[VO(5, Cl-Sal) ₂ -en]	> 300	12.54	12.68	6.82	6.96
[VO(4, OH-Sal) ₂ -en]	> 300	12.32	12.71	7.02	6.99
[VO(H-Sal) ₂ -fm]	> 300	14.67	14.69	7.99	8.06
[VO(5, Cl-Sal) ₂ -tm]	> 300	12.21	12.26	6.80	6.73
[VO(5,6 Benzo-Sal) ₂ -tm]	> 300	11.33	11.40	6.40	6.26
[VO(H-Sal) ₂ -o-Phend]	> 300	13.21	13.38	7.26	7.34
[VO(5, Cl-Sal) ₂ -o-Phend]	> 300	11.20	11.33	6.32	6.22
[VO(5,6 Benzo-Sal) ₂ -o-Phend]	> 300	10.75	10.60	5.90	5.82

* For abbreviations see fig. 1.

Analyses : Vanadium was estimated as V₂O₅ after igniting the compound to constant weight. Nitrogen was determined by semimicro Duma combustion.

Magnetic measurements : The magnetic susceptibility was determined in a Gouy Balance using G.R. copper sulphate pentahydrate (E.Merck) as calibrant. Magnetic moment was calculated from the relation

$$\mu_{eff} = 2.84 \sqrt{\chi_M^{corr} \times T} \quad \text{B.M.}$$

where the symbols carry usual significance. The magnetic moments are collected in Table II. Diamagnetic corrections have been made using Pascal's constants¹³.

Infrared Spectra : The infrared spectra of the samples were run as KBr pellets with the aid of Perkin-Elmer Infracord. Results are appended in Table II.

TABLE II

Infrared and magnetic moment data of oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes

Compound	C = N Stretch (cm ⁻¹)	V = O Stretch (cm ⁻¹)	μ_{eff} (B.M.) (°K)
1. [VO(H-Sal-NC ₆ H ₅) ₂]	—	—	1.67 (300)
2. [VO(H-Sal-NC ₆ H ₄ -pCl) ₂]	1600	1028	1.67 (300)
3. [VO(H-Sal-NC ₆ H ₄ -pOCH ₃) ₂]	1616	985	1.70 (295)
4. [VO(H-Sal-NC ₆ H ₄ -pSO ₂ NH ₂) ₂]	—	—	1.54 (297)
5. [VO(5, Cl-Sal-NC ₆ H ₅) ₂]	—	—	1.75 (295)
6. [VO(5,6 Benzo-Sal-NC ₆ H ₅) ₂]	1620	978	1.54 (297)
7. [VO(5,6 Benzo-Sal-NC ₆ H ₄ -pCl) ₂]	—	—	1.54 (297)
8. [VO(5,6 Benzo-Sal-NC ₆ H ₄ -pOCH ₃) ₂]	—	—	1.72 (300)
9. [VO(4, OH-Sal-NC ₆ H ₄ -pCl) ₂]	1628	990	1.68 (302)
10. [VO(4, OH-Sal-NC ₆ H ₄ -pOCH ₃) ₂]	1626	994	1.70 (302)
11. [VO(H-Sal) ₂ -en]	—	—	1.70 (300)
12. [VO(5, Cl-Sal) ₂ -en]	—	—	1.72 (300)
13. [VO(4, OH-Sal) ₂ -en]	1600	953	1.68 (307)
14. [VO(H-Sal) ₂ -tm]	1624	950	1.68 (296)
15. [VO(5, Cl-Sal) ₂ -tm]	1634	971	1.77 (295)
16. [VO(5,6 Benzo-Sal) ₂ -tm]	1600	971	1.85 (295)
17. [VO(H-Sal) ₂ -o-Phend]	1600	992	1.80 (295)
18. [VO(5, Cl-Sal) ₂ -o-Phend]	—	—	1.81 (295)
19. [VO(5,6 Benzo-Sal) ₂ -o-Phend]	—	—	1.76 (295)

Electronic Spectra : Absorption spectra were recorded in a Hilger-Waats UVISPEK Spectrophotometer using 1 cm. cell. Solvents used were of Analar grade. Mull spectra (liquid paraffin) of the solid complexes were measured in the same spectrophotometer adopting the procedure of Lee *et al.*¹⁴. The spectral data appear in Table III.

13. P. W. Selwood, *Magnetochemistry*, Interscience Publishers, New York, 1956, p. 92.

14. R. H. Lee, E. Griswold and J. Kleniberg, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 3, 1278.

TABLE III

Electronic Spectral Data of oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes

Compound	State	Absorption Bands (in kK) (ϵ molar for solution)			
[VO(H-Sal-NC ₆ H ₅) ₂]	Mull	21.74 sh*	18.50 sh	15.90 sh	12.00
	Chloroform		18.50 (170) sh	15.90 (96) sh	12.00 (48)
	Pyridine				13.70 (60)
[VO(H-Sal-NC ₆ H ₄ -pCl) ₂]	Mull		18.50 sh	15.90 sh	12.50
	Chloroform		18.50 (96) sh	16.90 (60) sh	12.30 (20)
	Pyridine				13.70 (40)
[VO(H-Sal-NC ₆ H ₄ -pOCH ₃) ₂]	Mull	21.74 sh	18.50 sh		12.50
	Chloroform		18.50 (160) sh		12.30 (46)
	Pyridine				13.60 (54)
[VO(5, Cl-Sal-NC ₆ H ₅) ₂]	Mull	21.25 sh	18.50 sh	16.40 sh	12.20
	Chloroform		18.50 (192) sh	16.40 (80) sh	12.20 (42)
	Pyridine			17.24 (134) sh	13.90 (60)
[VO(5,6 Benzo-Sal-NC ₆ H ₅) ₂]	Mull		18.50 sh	16.00 sh	12.80
	Chloroform		18.50 (154) sh	16.00 (120) sh	12.80 (70)
	Pyridine			17.30 (120) sh	13.70 (32)
[VO(5,6 Benzo-Sal-NC ₆ H ₄ -pCl) ₂]	Mull		18.50 sh		13.20
	Chloroform		18.50 (92) sh		13.15 (36)
	Pyridine			17.24 (128) sh	13.70 (60)
[VO(5,6 Benzo-Sal-NC ₆ H ₄ -pOCH ₃) ₂]	Mull		17.90 sh	15.40 sh	12.80
	Chloroform		17.85 (106) sh	15.40 (66) sh	12.80 (34)
	Pyridine			16.66 (72) sh	13.30 (26)
[VO(H-Sal) ₂ -en]	Mull	21.25 sh	16.95	13.00 sh	
	Chloroform	21.25 (88) sh	16.80 (160)	13.00 sh	
	Pyridine	21.25 (90) sh	16.80 (160)	13.00 sh	
[VO(5, Cl-Sal) ₂ -en]	Mull	20.80 sh	16.95	13.00 sh	
	Chloroform	20.70 sh	16.95	13.00 sh	
	Pyridine	20.70 sh	16.95 (160)	13.00 sh	
[VO(4, OH-Sal),-en]	Mull	21.75 sh	17.80		
	Chloroform	Sparingly soluble			
	Pyridine	21.75 (150) sh	17.20 (157)		
[VO(H-Sal) ₂ -tm]	Mull	19.20 sh		13.30	
	Chloroform	Sparingly soluble			
	Pyridine	Sparingly soluble			
[VO(5, Cl-Sal) ₂ -tm]	Mull	18.85 sh	16.10		
	Chloroform	Sparingly soluble			
	Pyridine	Sparingly soluble			
[VO(5,6 Benzo-Sal) ₂ -tm]	Mull	19.60 sh	17.85 sh	13.50	11.75
	Chloroform	Sparingly soluble			
	Pyridine	Sparingly soluble			
[VO(H-Sal) ₂ -o-Phend]	Mull	21.75 sh	16.40		
	Chloroform		16.40 (85)		
	Pyridine		16.40 (99)		
[VO(5,6 Benzo-Sal) ₂ -o-Phend]	Mull	21.20 sh	16.00		
	Chloroform		16.00 (110)		
	Pyridine		16.00 (160)		

* 'sh' stands for 'shoulder'.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Syntheses of some of the complexes studied here have long been reported in the literature^{11,12}. In addition to those already known, several new complexes have been isolated and characterised.

Bidentate, monobasic Schiff bases were prepared from ring substituted salicylaldehydes and aryl monoamines and they were next allowed to form a number of complexes with vanadyl ion under proper experimental conditions. The complexes are of the type $[\text{VO}(\text{X-Sal-NR})_2]$ (Fig. 1a), where H_2NR stands for the arylamine and X-sal as the substituted salicylaldehyde residues (X indicating the substituent). The quadridentate Schiff bases were obtained by the condensation of salicylaldehydes and alkyl- or aryl diamines and then the ligands were reacted with vanadyl ion in suitable solvents. The complexes are of the type (a) $[\text{VO}(\text{X-Sal})_2\text{-en}]$ (Fig. 1b), (b) $[\text{VO}(\text{X-Sal})_2\text{-tm}]$ (Fig. 1c) and (c) $[\text{VO}(\text{X-Sal})_2\text{-o-Phend}]$ (Fig. 1d) where en, tm and o-phend stand for the ethylenediamine, trimethylenediamine and ortho-phenylenediamine residues (cf. Table I).

Fig. 1. Structural representation of oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes of Schiff bases.

All the complexes are coloured and stable. The quadrivalence of vanadium in these complexes is proven by their paramagnetism, by characteristic vanadyl stretch and d-d ligand field bands. The magnetic moments of most of the complexes are in the region 1.67–1.85 (Table II), which are close to the spin only value for one unpaired electron as is expected for the vanadyl chelates. These near-normal values indicate that there are no significant interactions between neighbouring vanadium ions. Three complexes (Nos. 4, 6, 7, Table II) apparently show lower magnetic moments (1.54 B.M.). Some interaction between vanadyl ions of neighbouring molecules leading to lowering of magnetic moment is known to exist^{15,16}. The presence of monomeric VO unit is revealed in the infrared spectral data for the V = O stretch¹⁷ ($989 \pm 39 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The bands at $1617 \pm 17 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be attributed to coordinated C = N stretching^{18,15}, since free C = N stretch¹⁸ is known to appear around 1690 cm^{-1}

15. V. V. Zelentsov, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 7, 670.

16. A. P. Ginsberg, E. Koubek and H. J. Williams, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 1656.

17. C. G. Barraclough, J. Lewis and R. S. Nyholm, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3552.

18. B. Chiswell, F. Lions and B. S. Morris, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 3, 110.

(Table II). A confirmation of magnetic and infrared results is obtained in the monomeric molecular weights, reported for some of these complexes^{11,12}.

The interpretation of the electronic spectra of oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes is still a subject of continued investigation and discussion¹. According to the Ballhausen and Gray scheme¹⁹ band I ($\sim 11.5-14.5$ kK) is assigned to $b_2(d_{xy}) \rightarrow e_{\pi}^*(d_{xz}, d_{yz})$, band II ($15.0-18.0$ kK) to $b_2(d_{xy}) \rightarrow b_1^*(d_{x^2-y^2})$ and band III ($24.0-29.0$ kK) as $b_2(d_{xy}) \rightarrow a_1^*(d_z^2)$. Selbin et al.²⁰ suggested an inversion of the levels $e_{\pi}^*(d_{xz}, d_{yz})$ and $b_1^*(d_{x^2-y^2})$.

Electronic Spectra of all these compounds in non-donor solvents (e.g. chloroform) are essentially similar to the spectra of the same complexes in the solid state. Hence the configuration in such a non-donor solvent is similar to that in the solid state indicating that the solvent molecule is not bound to the oxo-vanadium (IV) ion.

The bidentate Schiff base complexes reported in this paper involve arylamines as the amine part of the Schiff base while those of Sacconi et al.⁵ and Yamada *et al.*⁹ are with alkylamines. All the absorptions bands in our complexes are not well resolved and the bands are often broad and show shoulders (Fig. 2 and Table III). In pyridine, the third band (appearing as shoulder in mull and in chloroform) is always masked, presumably due to its moving to higher energy or being masked by a charge transfer spectra. An overall decrease of the ligand field strength in the case of our compounds compared to the compounds derived

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of the complex $[\text{VO}(5,6 \text{ Benzo-Sal-NC}_6\text{H}_5)_2]$ in different media.

- (A) Mull spectra
 - (B) Complex (.005M) in chloroform
 - (C) Complex (.005M) in Pyridine
- Optical density for (A) is arbitrary.

19. C. J. Ballhausen and H. B. Gray, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, 1, 111.

20. J. Selbin, L. H. Holmes, Jr. and S. P. McGlyan, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, 25, 1259.

from alkylamines is indicated by an inspection of the second ligand field band ($d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2} \simeq 10 Dq$). Yamada and Kuge's complexes show 10 Dq around 17 kK whereas the complexes reported in this paper have 10 Dq around 16 kK.

These complexes may have more or less the same square pyramidal configuration regardless of the substituents (X or R) since they show almost similar spectra. The spectra reported by Yamada and Kuge⁹ for complexes derived from the Schiff bases obtained from substituted salicylaldehydes and alkylamines also do not show much dependence on the substituents. These five coordinated complexes can readily add a donor ligand in the open sixth site thereby altering the magnitude of the strong axial perturbation of the strongly bound oxygen trans to the donor solvent molecule. It has been observed that the pyridine spectra of the complexes are different from the solid state spectra and chloroform spectra. This indicates solvent coordination. On introduction of a ligand trans to the vanadyl oxygen band I ($b_2 \rightarrow e_{\pi}^*$) and band III ($b_2 \rightarrow a_{\pi}^*$) will shift towards higher energy whereas band II ($b_2 \rightarrow b_{\pi}^*$) may remain unchanged. The pyridine spectra of the complexes reported by Sacconi et al. and Yamada et al. fit well with this pattern^{9,19}. In Selbin's inverted level scheme, band I ($b_{\pi}^* \rightarrow b_1$) will remain relatively unchanged in a donor solvent. On the other hand due to weaker participation of the vanadyl oxygen in π -bond formation, band II ($b_2 \rightarrow e_{\pi}^*$) should be shifted to lower energy in donor solvents. The fate of band III is less predictable. The results of Selbin et al.²¹ and of McCormick²² are compatible with the above assignment. Boucher et al.⁷ have however observed a red shift of the first band and a blue shift of the second band in VO(tfen) in coordinating solvents and have used the BG d -orbital ordering to interpret the results.

The first two bands (wherever amenable to identification) of the complexes with bidentate Schiff bases (of : Table III) are shifted to higher energy due to complex-donor solvent interaction. When a donor molecule adds up to the sixth vacant site of the square pyramidal structure, a charge is built up on the vanadium atom and this would decrease the π donation of the axial oxygen to vanadium. Besides this, the equatorial ligand-to-metal interaction would increase as the metal falls closer to the basal plane of the square pyramid. This overall destabilising effect due to coordination along z axis, may cause not only the band II ($b_2(d_{xy}) \rightarrow b_{\pi}^*(d_{x^2-y^2})$) but also band I ($b_2(d_{xy}) \rightarrow e_{\pi}^*(d_{xz}, d_{xy})$) and band III ($b_2(d_{xy}) \rightarrow a_{\pi}^*(d_z^2)$) to move to higher energy. The shifting of the first two bands to high energy in pyridine (Table III) appear to be in conformity with the above discussion. It may be mentioned in passing that in the studies reported by Yamada *et al.*⁹, there are two complexes in which all the three bands have moved to higher energy.

In the case of the quadridentate Schiff base complexes we observe that all the bands are not well resolved into their components. The second band is easily identified, the third appears as a shoulder but the first band at lower energy is difficult to be characterised definitely. If the quadridentate Schiff base complexes of the above types are square pyramidal like those of the β -diketones, they should then readily add a donor ligand to the metal at

21. J. Selbin, G. Maus and D. L. Johnson, *ibid.*, 1967, **29**, 1735.

22. B. J. McCormick, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 1965.

the vacant axial coordination position and thereby produce a marked shift in the $d-d$ transition bands. Solvent effects (under the limitation of solubility) on the absorption bands of these complexes are however practically nil (Fig. 3 and Table III). Spectra of several oxo-vanadium (IV) complexes of quadridentate Schiff bases are known to remain unperturbed in donor solvents⁸.

Fig. 3. Absorption spectra of the complex $[\text{VO}(5, \text{Cl-Sal})_2 \cdot \text{en}]$ in different media

(A) Mull spectra

(B) Complex (arbitrary concentration) in Chloroform

(C) Complex (.005M) in Pyridine

Optical density for (A) is arbitrary.

A recent X-ray crystallographic study of bis (acetylacetonate) ethylenediamine Schiff base-oxo-vanadium (IV)²³ reveals that the coordination polyhedron is not significantly distorted away from square pyramidal geometry. Hence it appears plausible that the quadridentate Schiff base complexes in our investigation have more or less a square pyramidal geometry increasing the in-plane σ -donation to a point so as to prevent any further axial coordination by pyridine^{23, 23a}.

23. L. J. Boucher, D. E. Bruins, T. F. Yen and D. L. Weaver, *Chem. Communications*, 1969, 363.

23a. The crystal and molecular structure of N, N' ethylene bis (acetylacetonate-iminato) oxo-vanadium (IV) has recently been determined by D. Bruins and D. L. Weaver (*Inorg. Chem.*, 1970, 9, 130). The structural parameters indicate the absence of steric hindrance by the diamine chelate ring to the approach of a donor solvent at the sixth vacant position trans to the oxo-vanadium group in the square pyramidal complex. In keeping with our suggestion they point out a charge build up on the central vanadium atom, arising out of strong in-plane σ -donation and this is believed to be responsible for the solvent-independent spectra shown by the complex.

This indifference towards donor solvents poses a fresh problem. The refusal of an apparently six-coordinate complex to react with coordinating solvents to exhibit spectral modifications can no longer be construed to mean that it is coordinatively saturated. It may be a 5 coordinate species and may still not take up a sixth donor group.

In this study we have preferred the d -orbital ordering $d_{xy} < d_{xz}, d_{yz} < d_{x^2-y^2} < d_z^2$ to the alternative $d_{xy} < d_{x^2-y^2} < d_{xz}, d_{yz} < d_z^2$ because of two reasons : (1) the second band is not found to split in a lower symmetry field, instead it is the first band that often shows splitting or some structure^{5,9,24}, (2) the second band gives a more reasonable 10 Dq value for the equatorial ligands.

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24. O. Piovesana and J. Selbin, *J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 433.